

Impact on rice production

Since the late 1970s, drought has caused drastic cuts in rice area in Linyi (see figure). After 1982, TDCR became more popular and by 1988 was used by all farmers. Ricefields multiplied and rough rice yield increased year after year. By 1994 there was a 33% and 26% increase in per unit area yield compared with before 1982 and up to 1988, respectively. Yields of wheat following rice also increased from 1.5 to 5.4 t ha⁻¹. Therefore, profit increased by 22%.

Yield increased because the dry-raised seedling itself was healthy and mid-late rice cultivars would be planted in time to use their 20-d-longer growth period. Pests and diseases are insignificant and rotation cropping is improved.

TDCR has several advantages: (1) it is economical in water, labor, seeds, and energy; (2) it reduces costs and labor; and (3) it ensures a good harvest despite drought or waterlogging. ■

Agronomic package for hybrid rice cultivation

S. V. Subbaiah, R. M. Kumar, and S. P. Singh,
Directorate of Rice Research (DRR),
Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Yield stagnation or even a decline has been observed in many rice-growing areas, particularly in potentially highly productive areas. To increase rice production, a few rice hybrids have been developed and released in recent years in India. To exploit the crop's full heterotic potential, it is essential to develop a package of optimum production practices for hybrid rice cultivation. We therefore attempted to study nursery management, seeding densities, seedling ratios, transplanting dates, N management, and hybrid response at several locations under the coordinated rice improvement program.

The studies revealed that the optimum seed density of 15-20 kg in a 1,000-m² nursery and planting in the second fortnight of July (1 seedling

hill⁻¹) are ideal practices for obtaining superior grain yield in hybrids. The results also indicated that different rice hybrids performed well at different locations: Hybrid ProAgro at DRR and Faizabad; ProAgro and CRH1 at the Central Rice Research Institute and Chinsurah. The local standard HKR46 performed well at Kaul. These hybrids recorded superior grain yields and showed higher N use efficiency at these locations. Grain yield differences in the tested hybrids were not significant at Aduthurai, Mandya, and Pantnagar. As

the tests were made in the wet season, the hybrids may not have exhibited their full yield potential at Cuttack and Maruteru because of rain. The response to N was limited up to 100 kg N ha⁻¹ at Cuttack, Chinsurah, and Pantnagar, and up to 150 kg N ha⁻¹ at Aduthurai, Hyderabad, Mandya, and Faizabad. Hybrids failed to respond beyond 150 kg N ha⁻¹ at most test locations. Applying the recommended N in three splits (50% basal + 25% tillering + 25% booting) was the best management practice for hybrids in Vertisols at DRR. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — weeds

Chemical weed control in rice nurseries of the hill zone of Karnataka

M. Syed Anwarulla, NARP, Regional Research Station, Mudigere 577132, Karnataka, India

Weeds pose a threat to rice cultivation from the nursery stage in the hill zone of Karnataka (south India), which has 182,000 ha under rainfed rice (the sole food and field crop of the zone). This area is located between 12-14° N and

74-76° E. Average annual rainfall is 2,460 mm, of which 83% occurs between June and September (with the remaining 17% from October to December). Rice nurseries are sown from the first week of June to the second week of July depending upon the toposequence and rainfall pattern for the wet season and during the second week of December to the second week of January for the summer (dry) season.

Rice nurseries are infested by grass sedges and broadleaf weeds that

Table 1. Effect of herbicides on germination of rice and dry weight of rice seedlings in the hill zone of Karnataka, India.

Treatment	Germination (%) recorded at 10 DAS ^a				Mean of 2 yr	Dry weight (av) of 10 seedlings at 25 DAS (g)				Mean of 2 yr
	Kharif (1993-94)		Summer (1994-95)			Kharif (1993-94)		Summer (1994-95)		
1. Control, unweeded check	92	94	94	95	94	1.06	1.13	1.12	1.27	1.19
2. Butachlor preemergence 50 EC (1.25 L ha ⁻¹)	92	94	88	92	91	2.39	2.43	2.43	2.67	2.55
3. Benthocarb-30 EC (1.25 kg ai ha ⁻¹) preemergence	74	76	68	72	72	1.84	1.94	1.96	2.01	1.98
4. Pendimethaline 30 EC (preemergence) (1.0 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	72	73	68	64	69	1.92	1.82	2.01	1.98	1.99
5. Butachlor (5%) granules (25 kg ha ⁻¹)	73	74	77	79	75	2.12	1.93	2.20	2.08	2.14
6. Anilophos 30 EC @300 mL ha ⁻¹ (3 DAS) Postemergence	89	93	90	88	90	2.26	2.33	2.32	2.46	2.39
7. Hand weeding at 10 and 20 DAS LSD (P = 0.05)	92	93	93	94	93	1.94	2.03	2.10	2.19	2.14
						0.03	0.08	0.12	0.27	0.16

^aDAS = days after sowing.

smother rice seedlings and pose a threat when transplanted into the main ricefield, resulting in increases in the cost of cultivation and decreases in grain yield.

We conducted field experiments during the kharif (wet season) and summer (dry) seasons for 2 yr (1993-94 to 1994-95) to find a suitable herbicide to control nursery weeds. The experiments were conducted at the Regional Research Station, Mudigere, in a randomized block design with four replications and seven treatments. The plot size was 1 m² with nurseries grown under both dry (raised) and wet (flat) beds. The soil was a red sandy loam with pH 5.2, 78% organic carbon, 7.5 kg P ha⁻¹ and 68 kg K ha⁻¹. Seeds of cultivar Intan were sown during the second week of June (wet season) and second week of December (dry season). Herbicides were applied within 24 h of sowing, except for Anilophos, which was applied 3 d after sowing. A common recommended basal dose of

Table 2. Seasonal dry weed weight (DWW) and weed control efficiency (WCE) in hill zone of Karnataka, India.

Treatment	1993-94				1994-95			
	Kharif		Summer		Kharif		Summer	
	DWW (g)	WCE (%) ^a	DWW (g)	WCE (%)	DWW (g)	WCE (%)	DWW (g)	WCE (%)
1	142.4	–	102.2	–	132.2	–	96.2	–
2	52.6	63	30.6	70	48.4	63	26.3	73
3	79.7	44	59.3	42	86.3	35	56.4	41
4	83.2	41	46.2	55	78.3	41	43.3	55
5	71.4	50	42.3	59	68.3	48	38.1	60
6	56.6	60	32.5	68	52.2	60	31.3	67
7	50.9	64	28.2	72	45.2	66	25.2	74
LSD (P = 0.05)	10.1	–	13.7	–	12.1	–	14.0	–

^aWCE = [Control WW – treatment WW] / control WW × 100.

90-45-45 kg NPK ha⁻¹ was applied before sowing.

Butachlor 50EC and Anilophos 30EC had no phytotoxic effect on rice. The germination percentage of rice was higher on Butachlor 50EC, Anilophos, hand weeding, and control plots (Table 1). Weed control efficiency, dry weight of seedlings, and seedling height were also higher for these treatments

compared with the control (Table 2). Better rice seedling growth was probably because of the weed-free environment and better use of available moisture, light, and applied nutrients. From an economic point of view, nursery weed control with effective herbicides cost \$1.83 (Rs 55) per 750 m² area of nursery—the area required for a 1-ha ricefield. ■

Weed control in dry-seeded lowland rice

R. Rajendran and N. Kempuchetty, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

Traditional growers of transplanted rice in the Cauvery new delta zone of Tamil Nadu State often switch to semidry rice culture because of the nonavailability of water and labor. Under semidry rice culture, premonsoon dry seeding is practiced and the rice crop is submerged after about a month. A major constraint in this type of rice cultivation is high weed incidence.

We therefore evaluated five weed control treatments involving two preemergence herbicides followed by hand weeding, one preemergence herbicide followed by a postemergence one, a postemergence herbicide followed by hand weeding, and two hand weeding during 1992 and 1994 in September to January (late samba season) in the Cauvery new delta zone.

One unweeded control plot was maintained separately to assess weed control efficiency (WCE). The dry seeds of ADT 38 (135 d duration) were sown on a dry field and submerged after 1 mo. The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

The soil was a sandy loam. Thiobencarb was applied 6 d after seeding (DAS), pretilachlor plus at 3 DAS, and

2,4-D Na salt and bentazon at 25 DAS. Plots treated with preemergence herbicides were hand weeded at 25 DAS and the bentazon-treated plot at 45 DAS. Plots with two hand weeding were weeded at 25 and 45 DAS.

The experimental fields were dominated by *Echinochloa colona* among grasses, *Cyperus rotundus* among sedges, and *Trianthema portulacastrum* among broadleaf weeds. In the weed

Effect of weed control on grain yield, weed dry weight, and weed control efficiency in dry-seeded lowland rice in the Cauvery new delta zone, Tamil Nadu, India, 1992 and 1994.

Treatment	Rate (kg ai ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Weed dry weight (t ha ⁻¹)			WCE ^a (%)		
		1992	1994	Mean	1992	1994	Mean	1992	1994	Mean
		Thiobencarb followed by 2,4-D Na salt	2.0 + 1.0	3.8	3.8	3.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	80.1
Thiobencarb followed by hand weeding	1.5	4.3	5.1	4.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	79.6	70.3	74.9
Pretilachlor plus followed by hand weeding	0.3	5.0	6.0	5.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	89.1	80.9	85.0
Bentazon followed by hand weeding	0.8	3.0	2.9	2.9	0.8	0.8	0.8	54.1	59.1	56.6
Two hand weeding	–	4.3	4.8	4.5	0.6	0.7	0.7	60.5	70.7	65.6
LSD (0.05)	–	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.02	0.08	0.05	–	–	–

^aMean of four replications.